

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

PERIOPERATIVE GLYCEMIC MANAGEMENT OF DIABETIC PATIENTS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Isabella Alcaraz
Kathryn Fukumoto
Shayne Santiago

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Edward Waters, DNP, CRNA, Team Leader
Rachel McClanahan, DNP, RN, NCSN, Team Member

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Author Note

Isabella Alcaraz - <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9682-8766>
Kathryn Fukumoto - <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3162-6359>
Shayne Santiago - <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3185-9021>
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ABSTRACT

Perioperative glycemic management of Type 2 diabetic patients undergoing surgery is important in the prevention of postoperative complications such as infection, delayed wound healing, and increased length of hospital stay. Glycemic management in 100 patients with Type 2 diabetes having undergone elective hip and knee surgery was analyzed to identify current adherence to guideline recommendations for optimization of Type 2 diabetic surgical patients. Findings revealed that only 3% of patients had their blood glucose checked intraoperatively, and 20.9% of patients had BG values exceeding the recommended level of 180 mg/dL postoperatively. An evidence-based protocol suggesting increased frequency of BG checks, use of a basal-bolus insulin regimen, and subcutaneous insulin administration is recommended for optimization of glycemic management in this population.

Keywords: perioperative glycemic management, Type2 diabetes, diabetes mellitus, hyperglycemia, surgical patients, elective surgery

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Background

Diabetes is a chronic disease that affects 9.4% of the U.S. population, with a prevalence expected to increase globally by 55% from 2013 to 2035 (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2017; Guariguata et al., 2013). An estimated 10-20% of patients requiring surgical procedures are diagnosed as diabetics (Frisch et al., 2010; Jackson et al., 2016).

Surgical stress can lead to sympathetic stimulation and the release of catecholamines, cortisol, glucagon, and growth hormones (Palermo et al., 2016). A rise in the circulation of these factors leads to an increase in endogenous glucose production, transient insulin resistance, and impaired insulin signaling, which all contribute to perioperative hyperglycemia (Palermo et al., 2016). Hyperglycemia in surgical patients has been associated with adverse clinical outcomes, including impaired immune function, surgical site infections, delayed wound healing, increased length of hospital stay, and increased costs (Martin et al., 2016; Palermo et al., 2016).

Abnormally high glucose levels have also been shown to be a risk factor for postoperative sepsis, endothelial dysfunction, aggravated cerebral ischemia, and increase the risk of postoperative adverse events such as delayed extubation and compromised respiratory and circulatory function (Sudhakaran & Surami, 2015; Wang et al., 2019). Although the negative consequences of hyperglycemia in surgical patients are well-defined, perioperative glycemic management in diabetic patients remains widely variable.

Problem Statement

Current practice commonly implements the use of sliding-scale insulin (SSI) algorithms and discretionary intraoperative blood glucose (BG) testing for the treatment of hyperglycemia. However, recent evidence and organizational guidelines question the efficacy of SSI regimens and liberal BG control. Inconsistent implementation of glycemic management protocols results

in suboptimal treatment and adverse surgical outcomes (Colibaseanu et al., 2018). One meta-analysis of 11 randomized control trials (RCTs) found that the use of SSI in hospitalized patients did not improve BG control and increased the incidence of hyperglycemic episodes when compared to treatment methods utilizing longer acting or continuous insulin infusion (Lee et al., 2015). The basal-bolus insulin (BBI) regimen, which is a more physiologically-based treatment method, has been shown to improve glycemic control and decrease mean daily BG by 14 to 29 mg/dL in hospitalized, non-critically ill, Type 2 diabetic patients (Christensen et al., 2017). In diabetic surgical patients, the use of BBI was associated with improved post-surgical glycemic control, decreased wound infections, and decreased postoperative complications in comparison to patients treated with SSI (Phillips et al., 2017). Despite best evidence, SSI and random intraoperative BG testing remain common practice in the management of hyperglycemia during the perioperative period.

Current organizational guidelines recommend the adoption of a standard perioperative diabetes management protocol that includes regular point-of-care (POC) BG testing, moderate BG targets for perioperative BG management, and avoidance of SSI as the sole treatment of hyperglycemia during the perioperative period (American Diabetes Association [ADA], 2018; Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019; Umpierrez et al., 2012). For both Type 1 and Type 2 diabetics, the ADA recommends a target BG value of < 180 mg/dL for the majority of non-critically ill patients (ADA, 2018). Maintenance of BG < 180 mg/dL is associated with reduced stroke incidence and mortality risk when compared to a BG threshold > 200 mg/dL, whereas a BG target < 140 mg/dL was associated with increased hypoglycemic episodes (ADA, 2018; Buchleitner et al., 2012). Routine BG monitoring every four to six hours while nil per os (NPO) is indicated for all diabetic patients, with the administration of short-

acting insulin as needed during the perioperative period (ADA, 2018). While common practices readily accept BG levels outside of the <180 mg/dL target range, current evidence highlights the need to improve current practices to facilitate optimal outcomes in diabetic patients.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to identify potential gaps in care by reviewing perioperative records of diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery to (a) identify the frequency of hyperglycemia and BG measurements out of target range (80-180 mg/dL); (b) compare BG findings to consensus BG targets; (c) assess current perioperative glycemic management practices; and (d) propose an evidence-based glycemic management protocol for diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery based on best evidence. This project aimed to optimize perioperative glycemic control in this patient population.

Supporting Framework

Theoretical frameworks offer clinicians a systematic approach to solving a problem. Specifically, evidence-based practice (EBP) frameworks help to synthesize the best evidence, clinical expertise, and patient preferences to improve patient care (Schmidt & Brown, 2017). The Iowa Model is a well-recognized and validated tool used to implement EBP and improve the quality of care within an organization (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017; Titler et al., 2001). Comprised of five fundamental EBP steps, this framework involves asking a clinical question, examining current literature, critically appraising the literature, implementing a practice change, and ongoing evaluation (Schmidt & Brown, 2017; Titler et al., 2001). The current Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Healthcare (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017) aids in organizing the literature review and proposal for practice change (Schaffer et al., 2013) in this project (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Note. Permission to use model available in Appendix A.

Clinicians have recognized the Iowa Model as a practical framework for the implementation of EBP across a variety of clinical settings (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

The Association of Perioperative Registered Nurses (AORN) Journal published an article

emphasizing the significance of utilizing the Iowa Model to increase the implementation of EBP and clinical practice guidelines in the perioperative environment (White & Spruce, 2015).

Similar to this project's aim to address perioperative care in the diabetic population, the Iowa Model was used to develop and implement a practice guideline for patients with obstructive sleep apnea in the perioperative setting (Lemus et al., 2018). Furthermore, using the team-based methodology of the Iowa Model, Robinson (2016) demonstrated safer patient care after the implementation of a standardized perioperative handoff communication tool. Both pilot projects highlight the successful use of the Iowa Model and improved outcomes (Lemus et al., 2018; Robinson, 2016).

The stepwise process of the Iowa Model begins with identifying triggering issues to determine the project's purpose (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The increasing prevalence of diabetes in the surgical population warranted further initiatives addressing the diabetic patient's perioperative glycemic status (Frisch et al., 2010; Guariguata et al., 2013; Jackson et al., 2016). Likewise, optimization of the diabetic patient can help to avoid complications associated with perioperative hyperglycemia. Although the epidemiologic and physiologic impact of diabetes is well-known, perioperative glycemic management of diabetes remains suboptimal and inconsistent among providers. The primary purpose of this project was to identify gaps in current practice related to the perioperative glycemic management of diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery.

A fundamental preliminary feature of the Iowa Model is determining if the project's purpose is a priority for the organization (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). This topic is a priority due to the negative consequences of poor perioperative glycemic management, lack of evidence-based perioperative glycemic management protocols, and variability in practices

among clinicians. Identification of gaps in care and presenting an evidence-based glycemic management protocol can help to address this problem. Resources such as electronic health record data, which includes glycemic measures and current management practices, made this project feasible to complete (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

After establishing the project purpose, a multidisciplinary team consisting of three Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) student registered nurse anesthetists, one DNP certified registered nurse anesthetist team leader, one DNP graduate advisor, and one healthcare data analyst was formed. A comprehensive literature search, literature review, and critical appraisal of the current standard of care, clinical practice guidelines, and research on the topic were completed (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Following a review of the literature, substantial evidence was found to support the project's purpose, thus directing the next in the Iowa Model (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

The purpose of this project concluded with an evaluation of baseline data and recommendations for practice change (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). After obtaining Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval, a preliminary retrospective chart review of electronic health records (EHRs) was used to collect baseline data on various perioperative glycemic management measures in diabetic elective surgical patients. An evidence-based protocol for the perioperative glycemic management of diabetic patients undergoing surgery is presented. This recommendation is constructed from existing current clinical practice guidelines and evidence found during the literature review. The remaining steps of the Iowa Model are beyond the scope of this project, but offer an opportunity for the continuation of project aims based on findings.

Review of Literature

Overview

Optimal glycemic management is imperative in diagnosed diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery to reduce the risk of postoperative complications and improve patient outcomes. A review of literature was performed to identify the best evidence addressing complications related to poor BG control, locate consensus statements on optimal BG target ranges, and establish best practices for the management of diabetic patients during the perioperative period. Clinical databases searched included Google Scholar, PubMed, and Cochrane Library with combinations of the search phrases “diabetes,” “postoperative complications,” “perioperative glycemic management,” and “hyperglycemia.” Search criteria were limited to peer-reviewed articles, English language, and publication dates between January 2014 to 2019. A manual search was also performed to identify clinical practice guidelines for the perioperative management of diabetic patients undergoing surgery, as well as a review of journal article reference lists for relevant articles. Exceptions of publication date within the last five years were made for clinical practice guidelines; however, the most recently published guidelines were utilized. Article inclusion criteria were study populations of Type 1 and Type 2 diabetic patients undergoing elective non-cardiac surgery. Articles selected for final review included five clinical practice guidelines, five systematic reviews and meta-analyses, randomized control trials, retrospective observational cohort studies, and review articles.

Complications of Hyperglycemia

The negative impact of poor glycemic control in diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery is well-established. Diabetes has been found to be an independent risk factor for surgical site infection, non-home discharge, and increased hospital length of stay for arthroplasty, breast,

cardiac, and spine surgeries (Kremers et al., 2015; Martin et al., 2016; Schipper et al., 2015). In one national study of over 15,000 patients, a diagnosis of diabetes more than doubled the complication rate after ankle arthrodesis and total ankle arthroplasty, significantly increasing the risk of myocardial infarction, urinary tract infection, blood transfusion, irrigation, and debridement (Schipper et al., 2015). Increased preoperative BG levels have been associated with an increased rate of surgical site infection (Hwang et al., 2014; Kremers et al., 2015), while elevated postoperative BG levels increase the risk of post-discharge readmission and rate of infection (Jones et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019).

Complications of hyperglycemia were found to be most characterized in diabetic patients undergoing elective orthopedic surgery. Surgical procedures in this category included total hip, knee, and ankle arthroplasties and ankle arthrodesis (Hwang et al., 2014; Kremers et al., 2015; Schipper et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2019). In this surgical population, a diagnosis of diabetes and hyperglycemia (BG > 180-200 mg/dL) was associated with an increased risk of postoperative complications such as prosthetic joint infection, surgical site infection, and increased length of hospital stay (Hwang et al., 2014; Kremers et al., 2015; Schipper et al., 2015). The collective sample size of this population is over 37,000 patients from different countries, including the United States, China, and Korea, which minimizes the risk for bias and substantiates conclusions drawn about the effects of hyperglycemia in this patient population (Hwang et al., 2014; Kremers et al., 2015; Schipper et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2019).

Glycemic Targets

Glycemic targets are influenced by a multitude of factors such as type of surgery, duration, anesthetic technique, and anticipated resumption of oral intake (Joshi et al., 2010). In addition to these factors, clinical expertise also plays a substantial role in guiding treatment

decisions. Clinical practice guidelines are consistent in recommending a desired glycemic target ranging from 80-180 mg/dL for all diabetic patients (ADA, 2018; Inzucchi, 2011; Umpierrez et al., 2012). Once insulin therapy is initiated, the recommended target glucose range is 140-180 mg/dL (ADA, 2018). Glycemic control is classified as liberal < 200 mg/dL, moderate < 180 mg/dL, or strict glucose control < 140 mg/dL (ADA, 2018; Buchleitner et al., 2012; Inzucchi, 2011; Umpierrez et al., 2012). Strict glucose control is not routinely implemented due to a lack of clinical benefit (ADA, 2018; Buchleitner et al., 2012). Although there is some discussion in the literature as to which glycemic target is optimal, therapies should be adjusted according to the patient's clinical status in conjunction with established guidelines (Umpierrez et al., 2012).

Perioperative Management

Preoperative

Preoperative recommendations focus on thorough evaluation and optimization of therapies. Surgery should be scheduled in the early morning hours to minimize fasting time and disruption of treatment regimen (Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Assessment of HbA1c, BG, and adequacy of drug therapy is a critical component of the preoperative optimization of diabetic patients (Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). There is consensus in the literature to reduce insulin dosage and discontinue secretagogues on the morning of surgery (ADA, 2018; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Although the evidence is inconclusive as to whether metformin should be withheld on all diabetic patients, the Society for Ambulatory Anesthesia (SAMBA) consensus statement recommends discontinuation of metformin in patients with renal insufficiency or potential exposure to nephrotoxic agents (Joshi et al., 2010). As the patient is NPO, the modified insulin regimen on the day of surgery typically entails administration of 50% of the usual neutral

protamine Hagedorn (NPH) dose and 60-80% of the long-acting insulin or basal-pump insulin dose (ADA, 2018; Joshi et al., 2010, Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Administration of rapid or short-acting insulin is usually not recommended in the preoperative period unless BG > 200 mg/dL (Inzucchi, 2011). Initiation of a dextrose-containing intravenous (IV) infusion is indicated for patients undergoing major surgery such as chest, abdominal, vascular bypass, transplant, or any surgery with a duration greater than four hours (Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019).

Intraoperative

There are several insulin regimens that have been developed for glycemic management of diabetic patients: IV insulin infusion, closed-loop artificial pancreas, IV or subcutaneous basal-bolus insulin, and SSI (Lee et al., 2015). Although SSI is still widely used in practice, recent studies have found the regimen to be associated with suboptimal glycemic control and adverse outcomes such as infection, hypoglycemia, and increased hospital length of stay (Christensen et al., 2017, Inzucchi, 2011; Lee et al., 2015). Several studies, including a previous meta-analysis of 11 RCTs, have also reported higher mean BG levels and a greater likelihood of treatment failure in patients treated with SSI as compared to those treated with basal-bolus regimens (Lee et al., 2015; Umpierrez et al., 2013).

The literature is consistent in supporting routine POC testing at least every two to six hours in all diabetic patients during the intraoperative period (ADA, 2018; Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Maintaining the preoperative baseline BG in the intraoperative period is paramount as aggressive correction can increase the risk of adverse hypoglycemic events (Joshi et al., 2010). Although both IV and subcutaneous (SQ) routes are acceptable methods of insulin administration, the SQ route is preferred due to its predictable and prolonged therapeutic effects (Joshi et al., 2010). On the other hand, IV insulin infusions are

recommended for major surgeries in order to avoid acute BG fluctuations (ADA, 2018; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Practitioners may also elect to use insulin dosing algorithms that consider insulin sensitivity, which is determined by the patient's total daily dose of insulin (Joshi et al., 2010).

Postoperative

Immediate postoperative management requires close BG monitoring at least every two hours, depending on BG levels during surgery (Inzucchi, 2011; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Continuation of IV or SQ insulin therapy postoperatively may be warranted in patients with labile BG levels or those who have undergone major surgery (Inzucchi, 2011; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Once oral intake is restarted, it is recommended to resume oral hypoglycemic agents (OHAs) and other insulin secretagogues (Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010). Metformin can be resumed 48 hours after surgery in the absence of renal impairment (Inzucchi, 2011). BG assessment before discharge is recommended, especially for patients who have received perioperative insulin (Joshi et al., 2010).

Synthesis of Evidence

An extensive review of current literature and clinical practice guidelines were used to highlight the detrimental effects of perioperative hyperglycemia and determine the optimal glycemic management for diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery. Hyperglycemia puts diabetic patients at increased risk for adverse outcomes such as surgical site infections, myocardial infarction, urinary tract infection, blood transfusion, increased length of hospital stay, and hospital readmission (Jones et al., 2017; Kremers et al., 2015; Martin et al., 2016; Schipper et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2019). Management strategies found in current evidence-based clinical practice guidelines can assist clinicians in the optimization of perioperative glycemic control.

Perioperative glycemic management begins with clearly defining glycemic targets. Several clinical practice guidelines, often citing ADA standards, recommend the BG target of 80-180 mg/dL in most cases during the perioperative period (ADA, 2018; Inzucchi, 2011; Umpierrez et al., 2012). Notably, variable patient clinical status and external factors warrant ongoing assessment and adaptation of glycemic targets (Joshi et al., 2010; Umpierrez et al., 2012). Clinician awareness of BG glycemic targets allows for the apt implementation of glycemic management protocols aimed at optimizing the diabetic patient.

Evidence-based clinical practice guidelines serve as a valuable framework for the glycemic management of diabetic patients undergoing surgery. Quality improvement study results support the implementation of perioperative glycemic management standards for improving diabetic patient care. In several studies, adopting perioperative guidelines improved BG measurement frequency and mean BG values throughout the perioperative period (Hommel et al., 2016; Shah et al., 2014). Guidelines offer clinicians well-defined monitoring and treatment recommendations for the preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative periods. Preoperative evaluation begins with a thorough assessment of standard diabetes measures such as HbA1c, BG, and antidiabetic medication regimens (Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Preoperative optimization involves antidiabetic medication adjustments and preemptive treatment of BG > 200 mg/dL with insulin (ADA, 2018; Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010, Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Intraoperatively, guidelines agree that routine assessment of BG should occur every two to six hours for all diabetic patients (ADA, 2018; Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). However, intraoperative treatment of hyperglycemia is highly variable between guidelines with differing insulin dosing and route of administration recommendations. None of the guidelines or recent evidence suggest SSI as the sole treatment of

hyperglycemia (Christensen et al., 2017; Inzucchi, 2011; Lee et al., 2015; Umpierrez et al., 2012). Recommendations for postoperative management include continued BG monitoring, treatment with insulin as needed, and resumption of antidiabetic medications when tolerating oral intake (Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Ultimately, knowledge of current best evidence as reflected in clinical guidelines, can be used to direct clinical practice.

The purpose of this literature review was to examine the complications associated with perioperative hyperglycemia in diabetic patients and discuss recommendations for perioperative glycemic management suggested by clinical practice guidelines. Despite the known risks of poor BG control during the perioperative period, the management of diabetic patients remains suboptimal in current practice. Continued reliance on SSI and failure to adopt standardized management protocols may account for the lack of consistency in perioperative management among clinicians. A review of perioperative patient records evaluating the quality of glycemic management practices helped aid in identifying gaps in care. Additionally, the adoption of a standardized perioperative glycemic management protocol based on best evidence can further help to improve the care of diabetic patients.

Methods

The purpose of this project was to improve the perioperative management of diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery by first assessing current clinical practices through a preliminary chart review. Findings of this project guided recommendations for implementing a glycemic management protocol based on current clinical practice guidelines to optimize glycemic control in this population.

Research Design

The design of this project was influenced by a study conducted by Jackson et al., 2016, in which the authors performed an audit of adherence to a perioperative glycemic management protocol for diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery. In this study, 247 patients with diabetes were included over a two-week period (Jackson et al., 2016). For this project, a retrospective chart review was performed to assess the current state of glycemic management in diabetic elective surgical patients. This included 100 patients with Type 2 diabetes who had undergone elective hip or knee surgery at a large urban hospital chain in the Southern California region between January 1 and December 31, 2019. Patients with Type 2 diabetes were chosen over both Type 1 and Type 2 diabetics due to the significantly greater proportion of Type 2 diabetics in the United States. The CDC estimates that approximately 1 in 10 individuals have diabetes and that 90%-95% have Type 2 diabetes (CDC, 2019). In the United States, over one million total hip and total knee replacement surgeries are performed yearly (Kremers et al., 2015), which indicated this surgical population would likely be large enough to provide an adequate sample size. The number of patients that met the inclusion criteria for this study surpassed 100 patients; however, time constraints for data analysis limited the sample size to 100 patients. This preliminary chart review provided benchmark data for identifying areas for

improving patient care and helped assess current compliance with accepted standards for glycemic management.

Ethical Considerations

An application was submitted and approved by the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) and the California State University Fullerton IRB for assessment of human subject research. All data extracted from EHR had patient and provider identifiers removed for the protection of private health information. Patient records were arbitrarily assigned a number for organizational purposes. Data was gathered by Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) DNP students, with no affiliation to individual KPSC sites, and non-project associated health information was removed prior to data collection.

Sample and Setting

Data was extracted from EHRs of patients from various large urban hospital sites in the Southern California region. Criteria for inclusion were adult patients (≥ 18 years) with Type 2 diabetes who had undergone elective hip or knee surgery with a duration greater than two hours within the time frame of January 1, 2019, and December 31, 2019. Pregnant patients were excluded from the study because clinical practice guidelines are primarily designed to assist non-pregnant adults undergoing surgery (Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Orthopedic surgery, specifically hip and knee procedures, were chosen to be the surgical population of this study, as complications of hyperglycemia are well-documented in this group. Patients with Type 2 diabetes undergoing elective orthopedic surgery are at an increased risk of postoperative complications such as surgical site infection, joint infection, and increased duration of hospital stay (Hwang et al., 2014; Kremers et al., 2015; Schipper et al., 2015). Based on the review of literature, improvement of glycemic practices is imperative in this high-risk surgical population.

One observational study demonstrated that the implementation of a standardized glycemic protocol reduced the incidence of surgical site infection in patients who underwent knee and hip surgery (Agos et al., 2014).

Measures of Evaluation

Although methods of perioperative glycemic management such as insulin dosing and route of administration vary across guidelines, there is consensus in the literature on glycemic targets, frequency of POC testing, and avoidance of SSI use (ADA, 2018; Christensen et al., 2017; Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Clinical practice guidelines recommend that preoperative management of diabetic patients include assessment of HbA1c, BG, and current drug therapies (Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). Intraoperatively, a moderate glycemic target of BG < 180 mg/dL, routine POC testing at least every two to six hours, and avoidance of the use of SSI are recommended (ADA, 2018; Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019; Umpierrez et al., 2012). This retrospective chart review was designed to assess these specific variables and established benchmarks from which a glycemic management protocol and recommendations were developed.

Data Collection and Analysis

The identification of patients with Type 2 diabetes was performed using the International Classification of Disease (ICD) 10 code E11 (World Health Organization [WHO], 2016). Orthopedic surgeries included joint reconstruction surgeries of the hip and knee, as well as hip and knee arthroscopic procedures (Table 1). Charts were individually reviewed by evaluators to ensure that patient selection criteria were met. An anonymized data collection form (Appendix B) adopted from the region-wide audit performed by Jackson and colleagues (2016) was used to

obtain and organize information extracted from patient EHRs. Surgery-related data included the date, type and length of surgery, and type of anesthesia provided. Patient information obtained using the data collection sheet consisted of age, sex, weight, height, and the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) class. Data collected regarding diabetes management included a description of preoperative diabetes control, preoperative HbA1c, medication regimen, use of SSI or insulin infusion, and pre-anesthesia and post-anesthesia BG. Other data collected included anesthesia start time, time entered recovery, BG in recovery, postoperative BG management, and discharge location.

Table 1

CPT Codes

Surgical Procedure Category	CPT Codes
Hip prosthesis, Arthroplasty of Hip	27125, 27130, 27132, 27134, 27137, 27138, 27136
Knee prosthesis, Arthroplasty of Knee	27438, 27440, 27441, 27442, 27443, 27445, 27446, 27447, 27486, 27487

Data collection forms were reviewed to determine the incidence of hyperglycemia by identifying BG measurements greater than 180 mg/dL. The frequency of BG measurements outside accepted standards was noted. Treatment modalities utilized, including the use of SSI, were identified and documented. The frequency of POC testing was determined by examining the number of intraoperative BG measurements recorded and the duration of surgery. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the collected data. After a review of the results, a glycemic management protocol has been recommended based upon the best evidence obtained from a review of the current literature. This protocol will be implemented in future studies with the goal

of reducing the incidence of hyperglycemia in the intraoperative period by 25%. Subsequent steps that are outside the scope of this project include protocol implementation and assessment of compliance to determine if the outcome measure has been met.

Results

Data regarding patient demographics, surgery-related information, perioperative diabetes management, and postoperative discharge disposition was obtained for the study cohort. Patient demographics included 43% male subjects and 57% female subjects. The majority of patients were classified as ASA II (60%) and ASA III (38%). The primary mode of anesthesia was neuraxial (77%), consisting predominantly of spinal anesthetics. For postoperative pain control, 61% of patients were administered peripheral nerve blocks. Surgical procedures of this cohort were mainly of the knee (61%). For control of Type 2 diabetes, most patients were being managed with OHAs (51%). Only 4% of patients were being managed with insulin, and 9% were prescribed both OHAs and insulin prior to surgery. Discharge location was distributed fairly evenly between inpatient hospital admission of at least one day (53%) and home (46%). A full list of patient characteristic data is found in Table 2.

Table 2*Characteristics of Study Subjects.*

	All Patients
<i>n</i>	100
Weight (kg)	87
Gender	
Male	43
Female	57
ASA class	
I	1
II	60
III	38
IV	1
Primary Mode of Anesthesia	
General	28
Neuraxial	77
Spinal	75
Combined Spinal and Epidural	2
Peripheral Nerve Block Administration	
Preoperative	37
Intraoperative	1
Postoperative	23
Surgical Procedure	
Hip	39
Knee	61
Control of Type 2 diabetes	
Diet	36
OHA	51
Insulin	4
Insulin and OHA	9
Preoperative HbA1C (%)	6.5
Steroid Administration	
Dexamethasone	53
Discharge Location	
Home	46
Inpatient	53
Skilled Nursing Facility	1

Note. Values are given as mean or number of patients.

The frequency of BG measurements is categorized by perioperative period (Table 3).

Preoperatively, BG was measured in 78% of patients. Intraoperatively, only three patients had

BG measured, one of which had BG measured twice intraoperatively. Postoperatively, 67% of patients had BG measured. Average BG values ranged from 117 ± 32 mg/dL preoperatively to 157 ± 45 mg/dL postoperatively (Table 4). In the preoperative period, 7.7% of patients had BG measurements < 80 mg/dL and 6.4% of patients had BG measurements > 180 mg/dL. In the postoperative period, only one patient had BG < 80 mg/dL (1.5%) and 20.9% of patients had BG measurements > 180 mg/dL (Table 4).

Table 3

Number of Patients with BG Measurements per Perioperative Period

	<i>n</i>
Preoperative	78
Intraoperative	3
Postoperative	67

Table 4

Average BG Values and Baseline Values Outside of Target BG Range (80-180 mg/dL)

	Average with standard deviation (mg/dL)	BG < 80 mg/dL	Percent of BG values < 80mg/dL	BG > 180 mg/dL	Percent of BG values > 180 mg/dL
Preoperative	117 ± 32	6	7.7%	5	6.4%
Intraoperative	122 ± 31	0	0%	0	0%
Postoperative	157 ± 45	1	1.5%	14	20.9%

Data regarding the use, type, and route of insulin administration during the perioperative period can be found in Table 5. In the preoperative period, four patients received insulin, one of which was documented as SSI administration. Intraoperatively, no insulin administration was recorded for the 100 cases reviewed during this study. Postoperatively, 12 patients received insulin, one of which was documented as SSI. Of the patients who received insulin

preoperatively and postoperatively, 11 were documented as administered through the SQ route, and the remaining five patients did not have a route of administration recorded.

Table 5

Use, Type, and Route of Insulin Administration per Perioperative Period

	Preoperative	Intraoperative	Postoperative
Use of insulin	4	0	12
Use of SSI	1	0	1
Route of insulin administration	3 SQ, 1 unknown	N/A	8 SQ, 4 unknown

Discussion

This project identified significant gaps in care by reviewing the perioperative records of 100 diabetic patients undergoing elective surgery. One of the most notable findings throughout the chart review was the limited number of intraoperative BG checks. Only three of 100 patients had their BG checked intraoperatively, with an average surgical time of 180 minutes \pm 51 minutes. With guidelines recommending POC BG checks at least every two to six hours (ADA, 2018; Inzucchi, 2011; Joshi et al., 2010; Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019; Umpierrez et al., 2012) and average surgical times of three or more hours, providers should be assessing BG at least once intraoperatively. The postoperative period had the second lowest frequency of BG checks and the highest incidence of hyperglycemia (BG > 180 mg/dL). A total of 67 patients received postoperative BG checks, 14 of which had BG values > 180 mg/dL, or 20.9%. Preoperatively, 78% of patients had POC BG checks, with 6.4% having BG values > 180mg/dL. This trend of decreased frequency of BG checks in the intraoperative and postoperative periods with increased frequency of hyperglycemia postoperatively suggests significant room for improvement in glycemic management during these two perioperative periods.

Clinical practice guidelines recommend a glycemic target of 80-180 mg/dL in all diabetic patients (ADA, 2018; Inzucchi, 2011; Umpierrez et al., 2012). The percentage of patients with BG < 80 mg/dL in the preoperative and postoperative periods were 7.7% and 1.5%, respectively. Data regarding the treatment of hypoglycemia was not available for this study. Preoperatively, four out of five patients with BG > 180 mg/dL were treated with insulin. Upon reassessment, one patient had a measured BG within recommended glycemic targets; however, it is not known whether hyperglycemia was treated in the remaining patients, as BG was not checked intraoperatively. Due to a lack of testing, conclusions cannot be drawn regarding whether

glycemic targets were met during the intraoperative period. The lack of intraoperative POC testing may account for poorly controlled postoperative BG measurements, with 20.9% of patients having a BG > 180 mg/dL. Postoperative hyperglycemia cannot be definitively attributed to lack of intraoperative testing and management, as other factors such as steroid use and coexisting diseases may also influence BG. Nonetheless, these findings highlight the need to address gaps in POC testing to ensure that practice is adherent to current standards.

Clinical practice guidelines strongly advise against the use of SSI as the sole treatment of hyperglycemia due to poor glycemic control and increased risk of hyperglycemic episodes (Lee et al., 2015). Study findings indicate that SSI is frequently used in clinical practice for the correction of hyperglycemia. Out of 16 patients who received insulin in the perioperative period, 12.5% were documented to have received SSI. The use of SSI for the remaining 87.5% of patients for which a treatment regimen was not recorded cannot be ruled out. Conversely, 60% of the insulin administered was given SQ, which is in accordance with established guidelines. The SQ route remains the recommended mode of insulin administration because of better glycemic control and prolonged therapeutic effect when compared to intravenous insulin administration (Joshi et al., 2010). Findings related to insulin administration are only based on the preoperative and postoperative periods, as there was no record of intraoperative insulin administration. Implementing treatment regimens derived from established practice guidelines and current evidence will be paramount in eliminating the routine use of SSI and improving overall glycemic control.

Study Limitations

Potential limitations of this study include a limited sample size. Time constraints and restrictions of data accessibility resulted in limitations of the number of charts included in this

study. Additionally, this chart review was performed retrospectively and thus relied on accurate documentation of existing records. It is difficult to ascertain whether the records obtained were reliable. Inconsistencies in documentation such as lack of recorded insulin administration may underestimate the use of SSI, potentially leading to a miscalculation of the magnitude of this issue. Also, the high degree of variability for charting practices within the EHR may account for the lack of available BG values. Although manual data collection was performed by students familiar with electronic charting, the possibility of human error in collection efforts cannot be excluded.

Recommendations for Practice

Results of the retrospective chart review demonstrate that recommendations for perioperative glycemic management have not been fully implemented in clinical practice. Experts from the Joslin Diabetes Center have developed a guideline to support the management of diabetic patients that contains detailed algorithms on preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative glycemic management. In keeping with the three primary outcomes that were the focus of this study, the Joslin Diabetes Center guideline recommends a BG target of 80-180 mg/dL, BG checks every two hours throughout the perioperative period, and SQ basal insulin injections to maintain BG within defined targets (Joslin Diabetes Center, 2019). The guideline serves as a valuable framework that can be used to close identified gaps in care and assist in optimizing outcomes of diabetic patients undergoing surgery. The use of the Joslin Diabetes Center guideline, in addition to improvements in crucial areas such as education, training, and competence, will be essential in bridging this gap. Future areas of study will include strategies for dissemination and assessment of protocol compliance.

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APPENDIX A

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APPENDIX B
Data collection form

Field	Response	Explanation	
Investigator		Number <i>E.g. 01</i> The unique number assigned to the primary investigator completing the form.	
Surgery		Free text <i>E.g. Rotator cuff repair</i> The surgical procedure the patient is undergoing as listed on the operating list.	
Length of surgery	hrs, min.	Free text <i>E.g. 2 hrs</i> From anesthesia start time to end of surgery.	
Date of Surgery		DD/MM/YYYY <i>E.g. 10/10/2019</i> The date of the operation	
ASA Grade	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5	Choose one The ASA of the patient as judged and documented by the anesthetist anesthetizing the patient	
Age	years	Numerical <i>E.g. 45</i> The age of the patient in years	
Sex	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> F	Choose one Male/Female	
Weight	kg	Numerical <i>E.g. 87 kg</i> Patients weight as recorded preoperatively	
Height	ft., in.	Numerical <i>E.g. 5'8"</i> Patients height as recorded preoperatively	
Type of diabetes control	<input type="checkbox"/> Diet <input type="checkbox"/> Insulin <input type="checkbox"/> Tablet <input type="checkbox"/> Tablet & Insulin <input type="checkbox"/> GLP1	Choose one The primary way the patient's blood sugar is controlled in the community.	
Pre-op HbA1c (within 3 months)	_____% <input type="checkbox"/> Not measured	Numerical/not measured <i>E.g. 6.5%</i> Indicate the most recent HbA1c prior to surgical procedure date.	
Diabetic medication	Frequency	Taken as usual	Alteration
		<input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N	
<i>E.g. Metformin</i>	<i>E.g. OD</i>	<i>E.g. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> N</i>	<i>E.g. Omitted</i>
List the patients usual anti-hyperglycaemic medication including tablets and insulins. Do not include secondary prevention medication	List the frequency the medication is taken	Choose one Was the medication taken as usual preoperatively?	If the medication was not taken as usual, what was the change: Dose omission, dose alteration...
Pre-anaesthesia BG	____ mg/dL <input type="checkbox"/> Not measured	Numerical/Not measured <i>E.g. 115 mg/dL</i>	
Anaesthesia start time		Time To closest 15 mins	
Use of sliding-scale	<input type="checkbox"/> Pre-op only <input type="checkbox"/> Intra-op only	<input type="checkbox"/> Pre & Intra op <input type="checkbox"/> Not used	Choose one Was sliding-scale insulin used?
Use of an insulin infusion	<input type="checkbox"/> Pre-op only <input type="checkbox"/> Intra-op only	<input type="checkbox"/> Pre & Intra op <input type="checkbox"/> Not used	Choose one Was an insulin infusion used?
If insulin infusion used, substrate given		Free text <i>E.g. Humulin R</i>	
Use of IV/SQ insulin	<input type="checkbox"/> Pre-op only	<input type="checkbox"/> Pre &	Choose one Was IV/IM insulin administered?

	<input type="checkbox"/> Intra-op only	<input type="checkbox"/> Intra op <input type="checkbox"/> Not used	
If IV/SQ insulin used, substrate given			Free text <i>E.g. Humulin R</i>
If IV/SQ insulin used, dose and route given		_____ units <input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> SQ	Numerical/Choose one <i>E.g. 2u IV</i>
Intraoperative BG	Highest _____ Lowest _____		Numerical range If only one taken write this number in the highest field
Number of Intraoperative BG recordings			Numerical
Time entered recovery	_____ :		Time To closest 15 mins
BG in recovery	_____ mg/dL <input type="checkbox"/> Not measured		Numerical/Not measured <i>E.g. 180 mg/dL</i>
Patient discharged to:	<input type="checkbox"/> Home <input type="checkbox"/> Med/Surg <input type="checkbox"/> Telemetry <input type="checkbox"/> ICU		Choose one
Additional information			Free text If there is anything striking about this case which cannot be easily placed on the pro forma make a note of it here.